

Consent form page 1

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Consent form page 2

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PART II: CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Urban Agroecology for Health and Wellbeing

Please insert a ✓ next to each statement to show if you:

Agree

Disagree

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

3. I understand that that all the information I provide will be treated in confidence.

4. I understand that I also have the right to change my mind about participating in the study for a short period after the study has concluded [within 6 weeks].

5A. I agree to be recorded;

5B. and for anonymised quotes to be used as part of the research project.

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6. I agree to take part in the research project.

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Name of participant:

Signature of participant:

Date:

Name of Researcher:

Signature of researcher:

Date:

